

Governance of Climate Mobilities in Sweden: Discursive Trajectories, Emerging Trends, and Policy Recommendations

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Note

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List of acronyms

CBSS	Council of the Baltic Sea States Secretariat
CCM	Climate change and migration
DELM	Delegationen för migrationsstudier (Delegation for Migration Studies)
EBA	Expertgruppen för biståndsanalys (Expert Group for Aid Analysis)
EMN	European Migration Network
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FOI	Totalförsvarets forskningsinstitut (Total Defence Research Agency)
FUF	Föreningen för Utvecklingsfrågor (Swedish Development Forum)
GCM	Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration
IDMC	Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre
IOM	International Organisation for Migration
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IVL	Svenska miljöinstitutet (Swedish Environmental Research Institute)
MSB	Myndigheten för samhällsskydd och beredskap (Civil Contingency Agency)
ODA	Official Development Aid
RISE	Research Institute of Sweden
SEI	Stockholm Environment Institute
SIDA	Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency
SIPRI	Stockholm International Peace Research Institute
SMA	Swedish Migration Agency (Migrationsverket)
SOU	Statens offentliga utredningar (Swedish Government Official Report)
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

Executive Summary

Climate change and migration (CCM) have attracted growing attention in research, politics, and the media over the past decades. Governance is central to protecting vulnerable people and communities, and to pursuing just and sustainable development in this context. Existing research shows that two strands of narratives – the securitisation of climate-induced migration and migration-as-adaptation – have strongly influenced political discourse and policy. It also identifies four common framings of environmental or climate migrants: as victims, security threats, adaptive agents, and political subjects. While these insights are important for warning against oversimplified policy responses, most studies focus on the supranational level. National politics remain comparatively underexplored. Because governance includes not only laws and institutions, and because CCM governance is complex, multi-scalar, and fragmented, a broader approach is needed to understand how climate change and human mobility are governed in practice.

This report examines Swedish national politics to better understand the origins, trends, and trajectories of national governance of CCM. Sweden is a particularly important case because of its long-standing engagement in environmental protection, sustainable development, development assistance, and refugee protection. As part of the Nordic countries, Sweden has contributed to the recognition of climate-related migration in international policy processes. It also has relatively well-established institutions for addressing climate change, although the place of human mobility within them remains unclear. At the same time, rightward political shift and the geopolitical effects of the Russia-Ukraine war have created new uncertainties for climate, development, and migration politics, including Sweden's role in European and international governance of climate, development, and migration issues.

Drawing on the emerging climate mobilities approach, this report analyses national governance through the lens of multiple, interconnected forms of human movement shaped by climate change. It treats CCM as embedded in specific social-ecological and political relations. The study asks three questions:

- How did linkages between climate change and human mobilities emerge and change in Swedish national politics?
- How did the national politics reflect and contribute to the international mobility regime?
- How does the climate-mobility nexus fit or challenge existing governance institutions?

The report traces the evolution of policy trajectories and the effects of policy narratives across different fields and arenas in Swedish national politics, while also examining their interaction with regional and international scales. To address the cross-sectoral nature of CCM governance, the study adopts a mixed-methods approach. It combines discourse analysis of about 180 documents – including official reports, policy documents, and other institutional texts from the 1980s to the present – with four semi-structured interviews with senior researchers. The analysis covers multiple institutions and actors, including governmental authorities, development and humanitarian organisations, think tanks, and researchers, all of whom are understood to co-produce narratives that shape the governance of CCM.

The findings show that Swedish national policy and practice have long addressed links between climate change and human mobility, but mostly at the margins of political debate. The topic experienced up-and-down shifts, which can be divided into three broad periods: 1) 1985 to early

2000s, 2) the mid-2000s to 2020, and 3) from 2020 to the present. Across these periods, CCM has moved between three dominant policy domains: 1) environmental protection and climate governance, 2) refugee politics or migration questions, and 3) international development assistance and aid.

The term “environmental refugee” (*miljöflykting* in Swedish) first appeared in Swedish political debate in 1985 and dominated until the mid-2000s. Initially, the Green Party used this term in relation to droughts, and armed conflicts in Africa to call for environmental protection measures “out there”. In this phase, environmental refugees were framed as an aid and development concern, with a strong emphasis on solidarity, moral responsibility and historical injustice rather than national security. However, the narratives became quickly diversified in 1989-1990. Environmental refugees were used to suggest the relevance of environmental factors, such as environmental pollution and the Chernobyl disaster, in relation to potential population flows to Sweden from Eastern Europe and the Balkans following the dissolution of the Soviet Union and the Balkan wars. Concerns then shifted towards Sweden’s the preparedness to manage large-scale immigration. Left-wing parties proposed pragmatic strategies to prioritise preventive measures in the origin countries, and then support refugee camps overseas, and lastly open the door to those who are at the door. These developments were closely linked to international debates on environmental refugees, including alarmist population scenarios, and criticism of the UN conventions on refugees for not covering environmentally displaced people, creating terms such as “de facto refugee”. Political attention likely contributed to a significant legal development: in 1989, Sweden included a clause in the Aliens Act protecting people displaced by environmental disasters (Utlänningslag 1989:529, Chapter 3, Section 3, Paragraph 2). The existence of such a paragraph made Sweden rather exceptional internationally and in Europe, especially given the early period. However, it should be noted that the legal meaning of this provision was not clarified until the Proposition 1996/1997:25, which amended this law, and protection was later reinforced in the 2005 Aliens Act (2005:716).

After Sweden joined the European Union (EU) in 1995, left-wing parties promoted a European framework for proactively addressing the root causes of environmental displacement through development assistance and trade policy. Domestically, the legal foundation of protecting people displaced by environmental disasters was strengthened. International discussions of CCM, such as the 1994 Cairo Conference on Population and Development, clearly informed Swedish politics. At the same time, the Green Party criticised UN organisations for being reactive rather than proactive, and argued for recognising a good environment as a fundamental human right.

From the mid-2000s onwards, “climate refugee” (*klimatflykting* in Swedish) largely replaced “environmental refugee” in Swedish political discourse, reflecting the broader paradigm shift towards climate change as a dominant concern. Climate change governance became one of the major framings through which the issue was understood. The term was often used in simplified ways to signal potentially severe consequences of climate change, while its meaning was rarely defined or questioned. At the same time, calls for more research continued, especially to provide empirical evidence about climate refugees. This broadened concern across government authorities, development and humanitarian organisations, and think tanks, while also introducing a growing national security dimension. Many reports reached a similar conclusion: most people displaced by climate impacts were unlikely to come to Sweden, but climate-related mobility could still have indirect economic consequences for the country.

The late 2000s marked a high point of political engagement. In the context of globalisation, the Swedish government shifted diplomatically towards Asia, combining an interest in emerging markets with poverty reduction aid. This also redirected its climate migration focus towards Asia, especially Bangladesh which became a key symbolic site for imagining climate refugees and for designing responses. During this period, adaptation became a leading term for policy solutions mainly through development cooperation and aid. The notion of climate aid (*klimatbistånd* in Swedish) also emerged, including aid targeting climate refugees, even as financial constraints threatened to reduce conventional aid budgets. These shifts were closely connected to wider international debates on climate-induced migration.

During the same period, the *Riksdag* urged the government to address climate refugees into strategic international negotiations of climate actions. This constituted part of a broader strategy to position Sweden as a leading country in the global work of climate transition (*klimatomställning* in Swedish). Swedish politicians used multiple regional and international arenas, including the 2009 Copenhagen Summit, the Nordic Council, Sweden's EU presidency and interactions with UNHCR, to promote stronger links between climate change and migration in EU and international governance. Sweden's legal protection for people displaced by environmental disasters was often presented as good practice, despite the clause was rarely applied, and Swedish politicians took part in key discussions, such as Resolution 1655 (2009) *Environmentally Induced Migration and Displacement: A 21st Century Challenge*. Even so, security and preparedness concerns tended to outweigh humanitarian considerations, and policymakers preferred intergovernmental cooperation over a harmonised EU migration system.

In the 2010s, CCM lost visibility in domestic political debates, and there is little evidence that Sweden remained active internationally on the issue. Some reports continued to be published due to security and conflict concerns. Still, Sweden did support international initiatives, such as the Nansen Initiative, and the endorsement of its Protection Agenda. However, the 2013 EU Commission Staff Working Document on "*Climate Change, Environmental Degradation and Migration*" (European Commission, 2013) likely discouraged discussions about policy change within the EU by arguing that support should focus on developing countries where environmental displacement occurs. The 2015 European refugee crisis and the rise of right-wing populist politics further reduced both European and Swedish willingness to expand protection for refugee-like situations, and weakened momentum for international recognition of climate-induced migrants. In Sweden, the temporary Aliens Act of 2016 excluded the clause on environmental disasters, marking the start of a more restrictive approach in migration policy. Although consultation responses noted the potential future need for a national protection ground linked to climate change, the clause was permanently removed in the 2021 amendments to the Aliens Act in order to align Swedish legislation with the EU asylum acquis.

As CCM discourse spread across three main policy blocks – migration and refugee policy, development cooperation, and climate change governance – political shifts between these blocks increasingly determined how the issue is framed and governed. In migration and refugee policy, Sweden has supported global and EU-level work, while retreating domestically to a minimum national approach. A restrictive approach towards asylum policy is stated explicitly in the current government's migration policy. The current approach also highlights the role of aid and development practice for serving migration governance, which can be recognised as supporting CCM governance while avoiding any national commitment to integrate climate-related protection into any regular migration pathways.

Around 2020, attention to climate refugees increased slightly. This reflected both heightened concerns about the climate crisis, including extreme weather events affecting Sweden, and Sweden's efforts to position itself as a leader in the global climate transition. Although CCM was part of the exploration of systematically integrating climate-related security risks into development cooperation, this proved difficult due to the multiple meanings of security and CCM, which differ by policy area, level, and unit. Instead, climate aid, as one of the pillars in supporting Sweden's climate transition leadership, increasingly encompasses CCM. Many projects in disaster risk reduction and adaptation already deal with climate-related mobilities, but this fragmented approach is constrained by financial pressures and short-term thinking.

The institutionalisation of Sweden's climate transition governance has enabled more research and a richer understanding of the form and relevance of CCM in Sweden. Still, this new knowledge seems to have a limited impact on domestic climate policy. Instead, climate aid has become the main framework through which CCM is addressed. The strengthening of the climate aid approach goes in line with both the strategy of green transitions and the strategy of development cooperation for migration governance. This aligns with both Sweden's green transition agenda and its development cooperation strategy for migration governance. The growing emphasis on private investments, trade, and innovation within climate aid is reflected in the *Strategy for Sustainable Growth, Green Transition, and Education (2025-2029)*. At the same time, the *New strategy for Sweden's global development cooperation on migration, returns and voluntary repatriation (2024–2028)* frames migration as a strategic area of development cooperation. Evidence from countries, such as Bangladesh suggests that this approach risks becoming reductionist if it overlooks deeper structural changes. While CCM is increasingly discussed in Swedish academia, and extreme weather in Sweden sometimes necessitates mobilities, political debate still frames such movement largely as evacuation. One reason may be that existing political and institutional structures for climate adaptation leave little room to discuss mobility more broadly.

Overall, this report offers a nuanced analysis of how discourses on climate change and human mobilities have shifted in Swedish national debates. The nuances offer many insights into how the Swedish discursive trajectory is distinct from the international and European trajectories. The historicisation approach provides new knowledge on how debates on CCM are deeply embedded in changing national political dynamics. Swedish governance of climate mobilities is contingent and closely shaped by the interaction of three fields: refugee governance, development cooperation and aid, and environmental governance. CCM has appeared in many different political discussions, but has not produced sustained or far-reaching policy development in Sweden. Over time, the dominant norms have shifted from solidarity, unequal trade relations, responsibility, human rights, conflict, and security towards climate aid, green transition, and migration deterrence. There has also been a marked shift in the geographical imaginary of climate mobility: from seeing it mainly as an issue of the Global South to recognising that climate-related mobility also affects Europe, even though it is still rarely understood in these terms within Sweden itself.

The future direction of Swedish climate mobility governance remains uncertain. In the current political climate of restrictive immigration policy, it is unlikely that climate considerations will be included in the national migration and refugee policy in any substantial way. There may still be room for Sweden to play a constructive role at EU and international levels. The history of Sweden's former legal protection clause for people displaced by environmental disasters, rarely used in practice, but symbolically important shows the significance of legal interpretation, social norms, and political commitment to humanitarian principles. At the same time, growing

attention to national security and preparedness concerns may increase the appeal of reductionist and alarmist framings of climate-induced migration as a threat. A new mode of instrumentalising development cooperation through climate aid and migration governance, is taking shape. Meanwhile, some actors are trying to expand the definition of climate migration to include labour migrants working in green-transition industries, while discussion of internal (im)mobilities remains limited and displacement caused by land acquisition for green transition projects receives little attention. These developments should be closely monitored and debated to ensure that CCM is not reduced to a technical or economic issue at the expense of fundamental human rights, dignity, and justice.

The report proposes the following recommendations for Swedish policymakers:

- Deepen collaborations with other states, particularly within the EU and Nordic frameworks, to share data, align positions, and jointly design responses on plural and interrelated forms of climate-related human mobility.
- Develop an interconnected policy discussion for overcoming the challenges in this nexus topic as well as for addressing cross-sectoral needs. A round-table mechanism should be established to bring together relevant national and sub-national actors to share experiences and propose a common work plan.
- Ensure that development cooperation and climate policy explicitly address climate-related (im)mobilities, focusing on long-term and place-based structural change, resilience building and risk reduction rather than only short-term relief.
- Systematically identify where protection is needed: preventing displacement, protecting people in transit, and safeguarding those already in Sweden (including under other migrant categories), and link each stage to responsible authorities and tools.
- Support research on better understanding processes and trajectories of climate-related (im)mobilities, using an intersectional and agency-centred perspective, and generate more empirical evidence on how climate aid is shaping climate mobilities.
- Balance ‘green transition’ labour needs with protection. When linking migration to green transition labour demand, ensure this does not marginalise the protective dimensions of internal and cross-border human movements.
- Building on Sweden’s earlier experience with protection in cases of environmental disaster, explore innovative legal pathways and policy instruments (e.g. temporary protection, humanitarian visas, and complementary pathways) for protecting climate migrants.
- Connect domestic extreme weather governance with the governance of cross-border mobilities, and align CCM work with security and preparedness agendas.
- Pioneer rights-based climate mobility policies and research as part of Sweden’s broader leadership in sustainable development and climate justice in multilateral forums.

1. Introduction: a national approach to the governance of climate mobilities

Over the last two decades, mounting empirical evidence has shown that the impact of environmental/climate change on migration is real, despite complex mechanisms and challenging governance (see e.g., Cattaneo et al. (2026); Icduygu & Gören (2023)). While better understanding how environmental/climatic drivers interact with other migration determinants remains important, a broader view is required that de-centres environmental factors and considers climate change and migration (CCM) as a socio-ecological problem implicated in social and political relations (Boas et al., 2024; Daoust & Selby, 2024). To translate climate-change-related knowledge into action remains an enduring challenge: *what* should be done, by *whom*, and *when* are highly contested (Scott et al., 2020). Governance of CCM needs to carefully assess how climate impacts intersect with contextual factors such as armed conflicts, political and economic instability, poverty and demographic pressures. It also needs to pay attention to new contexts and forms of societal transformation, such as green transitions, that add new complexities to the governance of CCM (Vigil et al., 2025).

Governance perspectives are crucial but still emerging and not often explicitly explored in the growing climate mobility literature (Boas, 2021; Lindegaard et al., 2024). Governance encompasses a wide range of meanings, from political authorities, institutions, and organisations to norms and practices. The multi-scalar dynamics of governance mechanisms, operating at and across local, national, and international levels, profoundly influence both the structural conditions and the lived experiences associated with climate mobilities, revealing how power relations and normative frameworks collectively determine *who* moves, *why*, and under *what* conditions. Recently, the concept of “climate mobilities”, despite being new and contested, is driving some new directions of this young field of CCM. This approach calls for further engagement with this complexity by highlighting the plural and interconnected forms of human movement – such as displacement, migration, planned relocation, and immobility – as diverse responses to climate change (Boas et al., 2022). This conceptualisation and research agenda, which aims to move beyond simplistic and linear assumptions and imaginings of the linkages between climate change and human mobilities (Boas et al., 2019), opens new opportunities and places new demands on governance perspectives on the climate-migration nexus, both research-wise and policy-wise.

Research suggests that two strands of narratives – the securitisation of climate-induced migration and migration-as-adaptation – have strongly influenced existing political discourses and policy grounds. The securitisation narratives represent an entrenched linear, quantified and simplistic way of framing climate-induced migration as a threat (Bettini, 2013), often drawing on the notion of “environmental/climate refugee”, which tends to legitimise restrictive border control (Baldwin et al., 2014; White, 2011). Although this conceptualisation has been widely criticised in academia for distorting the social realities, and global and national policymakers nowadays accept that climate-induced migration is mostly internal rather than international, securitisation narratives are still emergent from time to time in different scales of political discussion and media narratives, feeding a complex reproduction of migration politics in the Global North while creating threatening and othering imaginings. However, research also suggests that international institutions highlight human security, whereas the EU perspective emphasises state security (Butros et al., 2021), highlighting the plural meanings of security associated with CCM. The migration-as-adaptation narratives highlight the agency of affected people, but at the policy level, it risks downplaying the responsibilities of authorities and powerful economic actors; by contrast, the notion of “refugees” tends to trigger more institutionalised responsibilities for protecting vulnerable groups (Bettini et al., 2017). Certain international organisations use the adaptation framing to gain legitimacy in governing CCM

(Schriever, 2025), while on the ground, it has also led to rigid policies focusing on sedentarisation and in situ solutions that paradoxically limit mobilities (Lindegard et al., 2025). Moreover, a nuanced picture suggests that the dynamics of policy and practice on climate-related migration can be understood through four distinct framings that emerge over time, positioning environmental/climate migrants as victims, security threats, adaptive agents, and political subjects (Ransan-Cooper, 2015).

Studies exploring governance in the European Union show that there is no coherent EU-level policy development on CCM; instead, policy discourses are scattered across multiple fields (Hahn & Fessler, 2023; Legut, 2022). Meanwhile, Member State policies are also not harmonised and differ significantly from one another, both in policy discourses (Nash, 2024a, 2024b) and in legal and judicial practices (Ammer et al., 2022). Given this complex and fragmented governance landscape, it is necessary to adopt a broader approach that extends beyond the analysis of laws, regulations, and policy frameworks to understand how climate change and human mobility are governed in practice (Lindegard et al., 2025). Research, in particular, indicates that the national scale remains understudied relative to the supranational or international scales in debates on CCM (Bettini & Casaglia, 2024).

This report focuses on the underexplored national political level as the primary site for examining the governance of climate mobilities. By focusing on Sweden and the period from the 1980s to the present, this report aims to systematically map how Swedish national policy and practice addressing the linkages between climate change and human movements have changed over time. The investigation is sensitive to how the two major narrative strands impact and are reproduced by policy and practice in the changing Swedish political context. This report thus seeks to develop a nuanced understanding of governance of climate mobilities as contextually embedded and reproduced across multiple scales.

The following questions guide the investigation:

- 1) How did linkages between climate change and human mobilities emerge and change in the Swedish national politics?
- 2) How did the Swedish national politics reflect and contribute to the international mobility regime?
- 3) How does the climate-mobility nexus fit or challenge Swedish governance institutions?

Sweden offers a particularly interesting case because of its highly relevant yet perplexing position on the CCM issue. The country has a long history of international engagement in environmental protection, sustainable development, development assistance and aid, and refugee protection. These issues are thus central to Swedish diplomatic strategies and the self-image in the international arena. Sweden used to have a generous immigration policy for asylum seekers and family reunification, as reflected in its demographics, which include 20% foreign-born residents. As part of the Nordic countries, Sweden has contributed to the recognition of climate-related migration in international policy processes, ranging from the Nansen Initiative on the protection of cross-border displaced persons in the context of disasters and climate change to the pledges regarding loss and damage associated with climate change impacts (Daszkiewicz et al., 2024). At the regional level, Sweden participates in institutional mechanisms such as the Nordic Council of Ministers and the Nordic Council, the Council of the Baltic Sea States, and the Arctic Council that discuss the regional relevance of CCM. Domestically, although adaptation to extreme weather such as floods, skybursts, and wildfires is being actively integrated into the national planning system, little is known about how this work addresses human movement (see Hamza et al., 2024). Meanwhile, recent studies warn of the displacement of indigenous peoples like the Sami by the growing green transition industries, expanding the scope of climate-related migration (Comar, 2024).

Recently, the intensification of shifts across several national contexts has provided additional reasons to explore the Swedish case. The Swedish government was long led by the left-wing Social Democratic Party and pursued a generous immigration policy, but this changed gradually, with the government often led by the centre-right alliance since the 1990s and associated neoliberalisation processes. In 2022, a centre-right coalition led by the Moderate Party formed the current government, with the right-wing populist Sweden Democrats cooperating in parliament under the Tidö Agreement (Delmi, 2025). The effects of this unprecedented change in Swedish politics are unfolding, including a more restrictive migration policy, lower commitment to climate action, and reduced aid goals. Sweden is perhaps no longer unique at the European level. However, it is converging with other EU member states in a trend towards welfare nationalism and a protectionist approach to border control and immigration (Kessler & Haapajärvi, 2024). Meanwhile, the Russia-Ukraine war and Sweden's subsequent membership of NATO have significantly reshaped thinking about national and regional political priorities. Preparedness and state securitisation are becoming the dominant discourses in planning across all social issues. Together, these developments tend to strengthen a state securitisation approach while demanding more national leadership (Elander et al., 2022).

Because there is no single overarching framework for governing climate mobilities, a key challenge in studying the topic is that relevant policies and practices are siloed, fragmented and spread across different authorities responsible for migration, disasters, the environment, development and humanitarian aid. The study applies discourse analysis to a range of official documents and reports from the 1980s to the present and draws on four semi-structured interviews with researchers. This analysis covers the policy, discourse and practice of multiple institutions and actors, including governmental authorities, development and humanitarian organisations, think tanks, and researchers, as these actors are understood to co-produce narratives in interrelated ways that shape the governance of CCM.

In the following sections, the data and methods of this report are first described. The findings then begin with an overview of the changing trend in interest in environmental/climate migration/refugees in the Swedish political landscape. Following three historical periods, the trajectories of policy shifts and discursive change from the 1980s to the present are outlined. In each period, the major debates and underlying justifications are presented, and the multi-scalar drivers behind these changes are interpreted. The discussion summarises the major lessons from the historical trajectories and comments on emerging discursive trends on CCM. The opportunities and challenges in Swedish policy and practice for addressing the linkages between climate change and human mobilities are also discussed. Finally, policy recommendations are provided based on the evaluation of the opportunities and challenges.

2. Materials and methods

Researching a relatively new topic, such as the governance of climate mobilities, requires a mixed-methods approach that draws on multiple sources and methods to map the evolving landscape. Materials were collected from multiple sources (laws, regulations, politicians' speeches, reports and news) between September 2024 and December 2025. The Swedish Parliament's database for documents (dokument och lagar) served as a starting point for exploring the visibility and contextualisation of environmental/climate migration in the Swedish policy landscape.¹ This database contains around half a million documents related to

¹ The documents were accessed through the following link to the database <https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-och-lagar/>

parliamentary work and has long temporal coverage. Six key terms in Swedish, “miljöflykting*” (“environmental refugee(s)”), “miljömigrant*” (“environmental migrant”), “miljömigration*” (“environmental migration”), “klimatflykting*” (“climate refugee(s)”), “klimatmigrant*” (“climate migrant(s)”), and “klimatmigration*” (“climate migration”), were used to search for relevant documents without limiting the time frame or document types. Other possible combinations of terms representing climate and migration were also tested, but the results were very broad, with many irrelevant hits. Thus, it was decided to focus only on the results based on these six terms. In total, 247 documents were identified.

The results were first screened to identify publication peaks, and clusters of document types. A subsequent discourse analysis was then carried out on a selected set of documents. This analysis involved careful qualitative reading of how environmental/climate change and migration are framed across different kinds of documents. It was sensitive to the context in which environmental/climate migration was named and articulated, and it interpreted how the narratives are shaped by multi-scalar actors and power relations (van Dijk, 2018). As shown in Table 1, the selection of the documents followed four criteria: 1) those in the first year when the search word was found; 2) publications in the last five years, 2021-2025; 3) those in the peak years; 4) Swedish Government Official Reports (SOU) offering an in-depth investigation of specific issues. After removing duplicates, a total of 142 documents were reviewed and analysed (Table 1).

Table 1. Selected documents from the Riksdag’s Open Data for discourse analysis

Key words	Environmental refugee	Environmental migration	Environmental migrant	Climate refugee	Climate migration	Climate migrant	Total
Hit documents	82	1	1	153	9	1	247
Selection criteria							0
1) First time	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
2) 2021-2025	1	0	0	25	3	0	29
3) Peak years	36	0	0	70	0	0	106
4) SOU	1	0	0	2	0	0	3
Selected documents (without duplicates)	39	1	1	98	4	1	142

Documents were also gathered from **two recent important conferences** in Sweden that focused on the topic of climate change, migration and adaptation: 1) The European Migration Network Swedish Presidency Conference in 2023 titled “Displacement and Migration related to Disasters, Climate Change and Environmental Degradation”,² and 2) The Swedish Red Cross Forum 2024 titled “The Climate Crisis as a Humanitarian Crisis”.³

Additional documents were collected from key relevant actors suggested in the literature: 1) authorities and organisations responsible for climate, development and migration issues, which include the Government Offices of Sweden (Regeringskansliet), Swedish Migration Agency (Migrationsverket, SMA), Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA), Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (SMB), the Swedish Climate Policy Council (Klimatpolitiska rådet), and the National Expert Council on Climate Adaptation (Nationella expertrådet för klimatanpassning), and 2) government research institutes and think tanks with or without government support such as the Migration Studies Delegation (Delmi), the Expert Group for Aid Studies (EBA), Fores, Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI), Total Defense Research Agency (FOI), The Swedish Development Forum (FUF), Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI), Research Institute of Sweden (RISE), Nordregio and Nordforsk. In total, about 40 such additional documents were used for analysis.

Four semi-structured interviews were conducted with senior researchers based in Sweden who have published on climate change, migration or CCM. This study received ethical approval

²<https://www.emnsweden.se/toppmeny/natverk/emnswedishpresidencyconference.4.4cda87071866b3f3f2d7c3.html> (accessed 25 October 2025)

³ <https://www.rodakorset.se/om-oss/seminarier/roda-korset-forum-2024/> (accessed 20 October 2025)

from the Swedish Ethical Review Authority (Dnr 2024-03890-01). For ethical concerns, they are pseudonymised as A, B, C and D. The researchers were contacted via email, provided with the project information and guiding interview questions. Upon written consents, interviews were conducted online or in person and recorded only for transcription purposes. The interview focused on the researchers' expert knowledge of the field and their experiences during their research processes. Although the research topic covers understandings of the political processes of climate mobility governance in Sweden, no personal political views were collected or presented in this report. The interviewees approved the references to them in the pre-print version, and the authors take full responsibility for the final content. Interviewee A is an environmental anthropologist focusing on the intersection of development and environmental questions in the Global South. Interviewee B is specialised in international relations and studies global governance in the contexts of disasters and climate change. Interviewee C is a political scientist with research focusing on decision-making and policy processes related to climate questions. Interviewee D is an expert in human rights-based law, policy and practice related to disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation. They have all been involved in policy discussions on climate change, migration and international cooperation in the Swedish and EU contexts, to varying extents and in different forms. Insights from the interviews, combined with literature, provide a deeper interpretation of the discourse analysis results.

The above research approach reflects the fragmented characteristics of the CCM topic in institutional structures. The selection of documents is not claimed to be representative. However, the comprehensive coverage enables a holistic investigation of the evolution of the discourse, shifts in it, and possible connections between actors and networks. Although there is repetition of information in the hit documents from the Riksdag database, it was carefully assessed to reduce bias in the results. This investigation is thus helpful for a deep interpretation of the politics around climate-related migration in the Swedish context. Most of the documents are in Swedish and were translated by the authors.

3. Findings

3.1 A marginalised while rhythmic topic

Reviewing documents from the last four decades shows that CCM-related terms have long existed in the Swedish political debate, but consistently at the margins. **Table 2** summarises the key characteristics of this pattern based on an analysis of the Swedish Parliament document database. The notion “environmental refugee” first appeared in 1985; “environmental migration” in 2016; “climate refugee” in 2001; and “climate migration” in 2009. The topic experienced up-and-down shifts, which can be roughly classified into three periods: 1) 1985 to early 2000s, 2) mid-2000s to 2020, and 3) from 2020 to the present time. The term environmental refugee was dominant before the mid-2000s, but with the emergence of climate change politics, the term climate refugee has almost become the only term used since then. The word refugee has also been used far more than migration when discussing environmental/climate change, which echoes the international pattern on the topic (Bettini, 2013; Hartmann, 2020), but it does not always suggest an alarmist securitisation tendency, as will be shown in the following findings. The old problem of mixing terminologies still exists, though much less nowadays. For example, in 2016, the term “environmental migration” appeared only once, in a discussion of Swedish competition and innovation in climate change and health research (Motion 2016/17:3564), which may be better termed “climate migration”.

The topic appeared in many different types of documents, which include motions, parliamentary chamber minutes (Kammarens protokoll), reports and statements (Betänkanden och utlåtanden), minutes of the EU Affairs Committee (EU-nämndens uppteckningar), Government Official Report (SOU), government bills and communications (Propositioner och skrivelser), interpellations, and written questions and answers, but did not make significant and in-depth steps in the Swedish political arena. CCM has rarely been the focus of these documents (with a few exceptions, such as Skriftlig fråga 2003/04:268, Svar på fråga 2003/04:268, Utlåtande 2006/07:SfU13, Interpellation 2009/10:177, Riksdagens protokoll 2009/10:69, Proposition 2020/21:191, Motion 2021/22:3410). However, it appeared under the main themes of 1) environmental protection and climate governance, 2) refugee politics or migration questions, and 3) international development assistance and aid. More than half of the documents were in the form of motions and parliamentary chamber minutes, which means the topic was part of certain proposals or debates, for example, for changing migration regulations or increasing aid budget, but often the motions were rejected. There were only six relevant in-depth investigations, including SOU reports (SOU 1999:16; SOU 2001:41, part 3; SOU 2007:60, parts 2 & 3; SOU 2017:77; SOU 2023:85). Among the six SOU documents, four focused on climate change, one on security, and one on migration politics. The Green Party has been the major party, if not the only one, to raise the topic. In more recent times, the Left Party and then the Central Party became more active on the topic. There have been several peaks in discussion on the environmental/climate-migration topic over time, while the arguments and justifications have shifted, as will be unpacked in the following analysis.

Table 2. Topic of environmental/climate migration in the Swedish policy landscape, 1985-2025

Key terms	Search term in Swedish	First time appearance	Last time appearance	Peak periods	Number of documents	Dominant type of document	Most relevant party
				1989-1990, 1996, 2003			
Environmental refugee	"Miljöflykting*"	1985	2025		82	Motion, Chamber minutes	Green party
Environmental migrant	"Miljömigrant*"	2006	2006	-	1	Statement	-
Environmental migration	"Miljömigration*"	2016	2016	-	1	Motion	Central Party
				2007-2009, 2019-2020			
Climate refugee	"Klimatflykting*"	2001	2025	2023	153	Motion	Left Party
Climate migrant	"Klimatmigrant*"	2009	2017	-	6	Motion	Green party
Climate migration	"Klimatmigration*"	2009	2024	2024	9	Motion	Green Party

Data source: Swedish Parliament database of documents and laws, last search date: 2026-01-09

3.2 1985 to early 2000s: claiming responsibilities for environmental refugees

The term “environmental refugee” (*miljöflykting* in Swedish) first appeared in the Swedish political landscape in 1985, in the form of a motion proposed by a Green Party member calling for fundamental legal changes in Sweden to centralise environmental protection.

“Over ten million people have fled their homes in Africa, and many of these are called, for lack of a better term, “environmental refugees.” They have fled drought and areas of land that can no longer support them. Others have fled civil war and oppression. The connection between war and natural disasters is intimate, and environmental protection is already being talked about as a prerequisite for preventing war.” (Motion 1985/86:Jo727, p. 8)

In this motion, people were portrayed as the victims of environmental degradation in poor developing countries; the problem was considered serious and urgent, but mainly “out there”,

still far from Sweden. Politicians drew on the term “environmental refugee”, Africa and conflicts for imagining the terrible consequences without environmental protection measures, but without aiming for how to deal with the situation “out there”. Such use of figures to illustrate environmental problems as real and severe is commonly found in various policy documents and political speeches from the beginning to the present day. Referring to reports by international organisations such as the World Bank, the World Commission of Development, or the Red Cross has also been a common feature across documents from the beginning to the present day, suggesting the impact of global discourses on national ones. Several significant geopolitical changes in the 1990s, including the dissolution of the Soviet Union and Sweden’s accession to the EU, have clearly affected the interests and ways of relating to CCM among Swedish policymakers.

Peak 1: 1989-1990: a solidarity-based humanitarian approach

During this first peak time, the issue of environmental refugees was framed in several ways, with different reasons for the causes, Sweden’s role in the causes, and the implications for Sweden. First of all, rather than the initial perception of the effects of environmental refugees as being “out there”, the linked effects on Swedish territory and the risk of environmental refugees from European countries were addressed. However, such concerns were not related to the securitisation of the border but rather concerned the need to update the humanitarian protection policy and practice to address this new phenomenon. Swedish left-wing parties expressed the constraints of the UN refugee convention for lacking coverage of the environmental refugee issue.

“In addition to convention refugees and de facto refugees, there is a large group of environmental refugees in the world today, with whom there are no good rules for how the world should deal.” (Motion 1989/90:Sf37, p. 6).

Differently, the Green Party framed environmental refugees as an aid and development concern. The impacts of environmental refugees were identified as mainly in the Global South. However, through a solidarity lens, the Global North should take responsibility for co-managing this emerging environmental challenge (Motion 1989/90:U220). The role of aid was positioned as reducing the exploitative use of resources and protecting the environment to prevent environmental refugees (Betänkande 1989/90:UU15). A Green Party politician questioned the reduction in the aid budget for natural disaster relief and environmental measures, including support for the growing number of environmental refugees (Riksdagens protokoll 1989/90:4).

Sweden’s responsibilities were motivated not only through a moral lens but also a historical debt perspective for contributing to environmental degradation in the Global South and further displacing people through trade relations. An example of the reasoning is as follows.

“Through deforestation, monocultures and soil depletion, and our exploitation of the natural resources of the Third World, which produces erosion and desertification as by-products, people in the developed world are creating environmental refugees, which are increasing every year, especially in Africa.” (Motion 1990/91:Sf627)

Another significant change during this peak period was that the term “environmental refugee” was used not only to refer to migrants from Third World African countries but also to migrants from European countries due to regional conflicts such as the Balkan Wars and the political changes in the Soviet Union. It was argued that, although economic, social and political factors may have driven these flows to Sweden, there was an environmental dimension, as some migrants might also have experienced the consequences of the Chernobyl disaster and

environmental pollution (Motion 1990/91:Sf627; Riksdagens protokoll 1990/91:57). Numbers were mobilised to imagine the scale and scenarios of environmental refugees. Social Democratic politicians gave a broad range from 4 million to 50 million to suggest the uncertainty surrounding how many might migrate to Sweden in the event of an important political change, and, more importantly, they warned of a lack of preparedness or plans for dealing with such scenarios in Swedish refugee politics (Riksdagens snabbprotokoll 1990/91:30). Sweden's refugee policy lacked adequate preparedness and concrete plans for handling such potential scenarios.

The above discussions of environmental refugees should be interpreted within the wider debates on Swedish refugee politics, which were driven by rapidly changing regional and global geopolitics at the time. The Green Party criticised the tightening of the European Union's (EU) common border, despite the removal of internal borders, as Sweden was still outside the EU at that time (Motion 1989/90:Sf615). Although all parties in parliament agreed on the three immigration policy goals of equality, freedom of choice and cooperation, different parties had different orientations, with some favouring more restrictive measures on asylum seeking and the criminalisation of migrants (Motion 1990/91:Sf24). The Green Party criticised Sweden's refugee and migration policy as outdated, as it did not cover new types of refugees in contemporary social reality, including environmental refugees (Motion 1989/90:Sf37). The term "de facto refugee" was often used to refer to those not covered by the Geneva Convention, including environmental refugees (e.g. Motion 1989/90:Sf37). The term "refugee" was also criticised for having multiple uses, ranging from internal refugees to economic refugees, and, legally, it was defined differently between the 1951 Geneva Convention and the 1969 OAU Convention (Betänkande 1990/91:SfU14). Thus, the parliament and the government called for further research on environmental refugees, which were assumed to be a large existing group in the world, in order to develop governance rules (Motion 1990/91:Sf24) as well as to improve conditions in the origins to prevent such occurrences (Motion 1990/91:Ub509).

At the time, a distancing strategy seemed to be emerging: upon recognising Sweden's limited capacity, even left-wing parties proposed prioritising preventive measures in the countries of origin, then supporting refugee camps overseas, and finally opening the door to those at the door (Riksdagens protokoll 1989/90:133). Despite varied positions on the justification for protecting people displaced by environmental causes, a significant legal step was taken to include such protection in the Aliens Act (Utlänningslag 1989:529, Chapter 3, Section 3, Paragraph 2). It is hard to pinpoint the specific event that led to the birth of this clause. However, it was likely the result of an accumulation of political attention to the issue, as described above, especially the Chernobyl event and the rapid shift in regional geopolitics after the Cold War.

“In this Act, a person in need of protection otherwise means an alien who, in cases other than those referred to in Section 2, has left the country of which he is a citizen because he

1. has a well-founded fear of being punished with death or with corporal punishment or of being subjected to torture or other inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment,
 2. needs protection due to an external or internal armed conflict or is unable to return to his home country due to an environmental disaster, or
 3. has a well-founded fear of persecution due to his gender or homosexuality.”
- (Utlänningslag 1989:529)

The existence of such a paragraph made Sweden exceptional internationally and in Europe, especially considering the time. However, the legal grounds were not clarified until the Proposition 1996/1997:25, which amended this law.

Peak 2: 1996: promoting an EU intersectional policy approach while strengthening national legal protection

Sweden became a member of the EU in 1995, and this change was quickly reflected in the way migration and refugee politics were articulated. Swedish refugee policy sought to uphold international commitments and actively develop EU cooperation while strengthening Swedish political traditions on environmental and refugee issues. The increasing complexity of global population movements was recognised as being caused by the intersection of population growth, poverty, conflicts and environmental degradation, plus the globalised economy and development of communications and transport technologies (Proposition 1996/97:25). The international processes of environmental governance, such as the 1994 Cairo Conference on Population and Development, which strongly connected environmental change to migration, informed the Swedish politics. Environmental refugees were asked to be seen as part of this broader, changing picture of migration, with many driving forces in globalisation.

“More and more people in the world will move within or between countries in the coming decades. The number of migrants now constitutes about 2.5 per cent of the world’s population. The refugee situation continues to worsen. About ten years ago, there were about 10 million refugees; now there are about 23 million. In addition, there are about 2.5 million Palestinian refugees and about 25 million internal refugees (within their own country). The number of environmental refugees is estimated at 25 million.” (SOU 1995:75, p. 313)

The scope of environmental refugees was estimated to increase and become globally distributed, with severe risk projections associated with environmental catastrophes. At the same time, it was emphasised that only a small percentage of refugees would reach industrialised countries. UN organisations were criticised for addressing displacement and migration only after they occur, and, with the advance of environmental concerns in global politics, the Green Party argued for including a good environment as a fundamental human right in human rights conventions (Betänkande 1996/97:UU12).

As Sweden became part of the EU, the tighter common border led to increased rejections, a reduced number of asylum seekers, and the deportation of refugees (Motion 1989/90:Sf615), which suggested a general restrictive turn at the EU level towards refugees, including on environmental grounds. Swedish left-wing parties criticised this while they instead argued for moving from a reactive refugee policy approach to a preventive one, with the latter focusing on the origin countries by addressing the root causes of environmental refugees and providing protection and support for them to stay in the origins (Proposition 1996/97:25). Following this logic, an effective cooperation system was called on at the EU level to coordinate foreign policy, development assistance, trade policy and security policy.

Besides international and EU commitments, the Swedish politicians continued to emphasise the long tradition and coherence of Swedish refugee policy. Thus, the term “environmental refugee” was highlighted as a new issue that the Swedish refugee policy should address.

“The parliament, in its opinion, informs the government of what is stated in the motion that environmental refugees, homosexuals and others who are persecuted on the grounds of their gender can be included under the concept of convention refugees”. (Betänkande 1996/97:SfU5)

During this period, there were continued efforts to improve legal certainty in the asylum process, including for people seeking protection as environmental refugees. Proposition 1996/97:25,

Swedish Migration in Global Perspective, is often considered the real start of Sweden's legal provisions for disaster displacement. This proposition clarified the legal basis for this provision and directed decision-makers to consider principles derived from international refugee law and international human rights law when applying it (Scott & Garner, 2022). In the government investigation report *Increased Legal Certainty in Asylum Cases* (SOU1999:16, part II, p.420), it was clarified that, following the 1995 amendments to the Aliens Act, residence permits for war and environmental refugees may be refused on criminal grounds. This indicates that the Swedish government sought to balance humanitarian protection with concerns about public order and safety. In 1997, the categorisation of persons in need of protection was changed, and such conditions applied to persons in need of protection according to Chapter 3, Section 3, first paragraph 2, i.e. those who, due to an external or internal armed conflict, need protection or due to an environmental disaster, cannot return to their home country.

Peak 3: 2003: CCM once as a question at focus

For the first time in the Swedish political arena, a written question in 2003 explicitly focused on CCM. Drawing on the example of Tuvalu, a Left Party member asked the foreign affairs minister whether Sweden would work internationally to expand the Geneva Convention to protect people who are forced to move for environmental reasons, so-called “environmental refugees”, and called on the developed world to assume responsibility for its contribution to climate change and its consequences (Skriftlig fråga 2003/04:268). In the minister's reply to the answer, it was highlighted that involuntary migration, with environmental factors among the causes, had been noted and discussed in Swedish politics for years. In particular, Sweden had an explicit provision in the Aliens Act since 1997 that protects those who, due to an environmental disaster, cannot return to their home country.

“This concerns protection in the event of a sudden disaster, which means that it would be contrary to the demands of humanity to immediately send someone back to the country where the disaster occurred. However, this does not apply to cases where, for example, a continuous deterioration in the conditions for food production in a country leads to severe supply problems there.” (Svar på fråga 2003/04:268).

However, it was also clearly stated that the government did not believe there were conditions in place to create international agreements to protect environmental refugees. It was also not appropriate to expand the Geneva Convention for this purpose. Instead, other regional and international legal efforts should be made to supplement the protections provided by the Geneva Convention.

Legalwise, the Alien Act (2005:716) updated Chapter 4, Section 2, paragraph 2 to continue to protect an alien outside the alien's country of nationality if he or she is unable to return to the country of origin because of an environmental disaster (SFS 2005:716).

Box 1. Key findings in period 1 (1985 to the early 2000s)

- The notion of “environmental refugee” first appeared in 1985, suggesting an “out there” distant problem in the Global South, especially Africa.
- The discourse of environmental refugee was not only limited to the Global South but followed the dynamics of geopolitics and refugee flows to Sweden, such as being connected to the dissolution of the Soviet Union and the Balkan wars.
- The human face of environmental problems already existed in the early phase.
- The topic was framed under three themes – environmental protection, refugee politics and development assistance and aid – and the importance shifted upon changing regional and international contexts.
- Although numbers and scenarios were used to alarm about the large-scale population flows and severe consequences, they were mainly used as a base to argue for a proactive approach. However, concerns about a security threat emerged with European geopolitical instabilities.
- Responsibilities for helping environmental refugees were reasoned not only as a moral must and a solidarity stance but also as a matter of justice due to exploitative trade relationships.
- The legal protection for people displaced by environmental disasters was provided by the Aliens Act 1989 and strengthened through legal changes in 1995 and 1997.
- The lack of coverage on environmental refugees by the international refugee conventions was criticised, creating the term “de facto refugee” and raising arguments for a good environment to be included in international human rights conventions.
- After joining the EU in 1995, Swedish left-wing parties promoted a cooperation system at the EU level to take a proactive and preventive approach to address the root causes of environmental refugees in the origins through development assistance and trade policy.
- Despite being largely a marginal topic, there was a short explicit question in 2003 to the government, asking if it would work for the expansion of the Geneva Convention to cover people displaced by climate change. The government denied it and would rather pursue alternative regional and international ways.

3.3 Mid-2000s to 2020: strategic protection of climate refugees for leading climate change transitions

From the 2000s onwards, the term “climate refugee” (*klimatflykting* in Swedish) gradually emerged and replaced “environmental refugee” in political discourse. It first appeared in 2001 in a government investigation report (SOU2001: 41), which examined vulnerabilities and security issues to achieve a more holistic view of civil defence planning and preparedness in peacetime.

“The effects of climate change in our environment can lead to changed conditions and reduce the possibilities for sustainable agriculture and forestry. This can then lead to an increase in the number of climate refugees. The risks of large-scale regional conflicts in our immediate area cannot be ruled out.” (SOU 2001:41, p.268)

During this period, references to the term “climate refugee” were marginal in almost all documents. It was used as a side and simplified illustration of the potentially serious consequences of climate change, with its meaning rarely explained and treated as self-evident. Figures and regional examples of climate-induced migration were also frequently cited at random without specifying the source. For example, in a 2004 parliamentary chamber minutes, a Green Party member illustrated the challenging greenhouse effects as making “25 million suffering climate refugees on our planet. The number is only increasing as people flee from droughts or floods.” (Riksdagens protokoll 2004/05:140, p 35). However, in a 2005 report, a much larger figure of 50 million environmental refugees expected globally due to climate change is mentioned, with only a vague reference to a UN report (Riksdagens protokoll 2005/06:13).

Over the past 20 years, from the mid-2000s onward, there were two peak periods in discussions of climate refugees. Interestingly, these two peak times demonstrate contrasting sets of framing, reasoning and justification on the governance of CCM.

Peak 1: 2007-2009: turning towards Asia and institutionalisation efforts

The rapid expansion of global debates on climate change strongly encouraged Swedish political discourse to shift from talking about environmental problems/refugees to climate problems/refugees. The awarding of the Nobel Peace Prize to Al Gore and the IPCC in 2007 provided additional momentum in the political debate to demand actions for climate change. In the parliament debate on migration, a Green Party politician said the following:

“Al Gore also spoke about climate refugees, citing Darfur as a clear example of how climate change also fuels or creates conflict. He said that a 1-meter rise in sea levels will create 100 million new climate refugees, and 6 meters, which is possible, will create 450 million new climate refugees.” (Betänkande 2007/08:SfU2)

Climate change governance became a major framing of the climate refugee topic. The Swedish government was eager to gain an overall picture of the threats and opportunities Sweden faces from climate change, and a major SOU report, composed of three parts, was published in 2007. In Part II, section 4.7, which presents changes in the world that affect Sweden, a brief subsection focused on the impact on migration patterns (SOU2007:60, Part II, p. 465). Acknowledging uncertainties in research on issues such as the scale of refugee movements and the directions of flows, the report concluded that climate refugees were a regional phenomenon in the Global South. People fleeing were either internally displaced or ended up in refugee camps, and were less likely to come to Sweden. In the Global South, climate refugees are likely to intensify urbanisation and conflicts, and thus aid works are needed to limit such negative effects (ibid., p. 469). Still, the economic costs of climate change, including conflicts and climate refugees, would be high and have indirect effects on Sweden (SOU2007:60, Part III, p. 641). In a later report from the Swedish Civil Defence and Resilience Agency (MSB, 2012), which assesses the impact of climate change on Swedish public safety and preparedness, it is stated that large-scale migration due to climate change lacks scientific support and that it is uncertain how this would affect Sweden. Studies by Swedish research institutes, such as Mobjörk and Simonsson (2011), claim that migration flows increased due to globalisation. However, it is hard to separate

climate factors from other causes of migration, making it even more difficult to predict the impact on Sweden.

In the new context of globalisation, the Swedish government pursued a strategic diplomatic shift towards Asia, targeting both emerging markets and aid for poverty reduction, which also steered its geographical focus on climate refugees towards Asia (Riksdagens protokoll 2009/10:89). In contrast, earlier debates had illustrated environmental degradation mainly through disasters such as drought and earthquakes, sea-level rise and floods became the new main symbols of climate change effects. Together, these developments justified greater attention to Asia. “Especially in Asia, environmental threats are imminent. If nothing is done, we will see millions of climate refugees and environmental disasters that we now find difficult to imagine” (Motion 2007/08:U359). The notion of adaptation emerged during this period and was frequently linked to measures in development assistance and aid aimed at addressing climate change (e.g., Ds 2007:46). From this time, left-wing parties began using the concept of climate aid (*klimatbistånd* in Swedish). While emphasising that climate aid would constitute an important part of development cooperation, including assistance to climate refugees, they criticised the reduction in the budget for conventional aid work (Riksdagens protokoll 2008/09:132).

Box 2. Bangladesh as a symbolic place for imagining climate refugees and a site for development interventions

During the peak period 2007-2009 in the Swedish political arena, Bangladesh emerged as a new symbol for referring to climate-related migration, as well as a key site for probing ways of working with the issue. Below are some example quotes.

“There are calculations that say that the rise in sea levels will put parts of Bangladesh under water by 2050 and create a number of so-called climate refugees. Further effects may be that desert areas expand and that Himalayan glaciers melt faster.” (Ds 2007:46)

“The countries that emit the most greenhouse gases (Sweden 8, the EU just over 10 and the USA 20 tons of greenhouse gases per person per year) are the ones that are least affected by the greenhouse effect. At the same time, climate change is already leading to humanitarian disasters today, as thousands of people are forced to flee their flooded homes in Bangladesh (with emissions of 0.2 tons of greenhouse gases per person per year). In the future, it is estimated that up to 40 million of the country’s inhabitants will become climate refugees when large parts of Bangladesh are submerged.” (Motion 2008/09:MJ18)

“We regularly receive visits from representatives from many different countries here at the Riksdagshuset. Yesterday, for example, we had a visit from Bangladesh. It was a woman who described how the situation there is worsening and how climate change primarily affects women and children, despite the efforts made by the international community.” (Riksdagens protocol 2009/10:18)

“Bangladesh is another country where they now have very good, I would say, adaptation plans. They are looking at the vulnerability. They know that there are many poor people who will be hit the hardest and do not have the capacity to support themselves. They will have to move people from water and delta areas further up and further away.” (Protokoll 2009/10:69)

Internationally, addressing the issue of climate refugees was in the interest of keeping Sweden's leadership in climate transition (*klimatomställning* in Swedish). As a Green Party member argued strongly in a parliamentary debate:

“It is not long ago that we were forced to stand in the rostrum and defend climate problems against climate deniers, who claimed that the problems did not exist. Both the Prime Minister and the Minister of the Environment have stated on many occasions that Sweden should be a pioneer country when it comes to climate transition work.” (Riksdagens protokoll 2007/08:87, p. 193)

Climate refugees were explicitly called for inclusion in strategic international negotiations on climate action. The Riksdag urged the government to push in international forums for countries to accept climate refugees in relation to their own emissions.

“There was also talk of environmental and climate refugees. We will see an increase in the number of people leaving their home countries due to a changing climate. The greens of the world have an idea about how we can solve this. The minister could perhaps use it to scare the US and others, at least. People should be accepted in proportion to the amount of emissions that each country has caused. That would mean that the US would have to accept a lot of people.” (Riksdagens protokoll 2007/08:129, p. 132).

At the supranational level, Swedish politicians also actively engaged with the topic through the Nordic Council. Work on climate migration was said to start from 2006 (Riksdagens protocol 2009/10:18). In 2007, the council adopted a recommendation to the Nordic governments that, the Nordic countries should take a joint initiative within the EU to raise the issue with the UN, to establish some form of worldwide roundtable discussion on how climate migration can be taken care of by the international community, to address the structures and regulations for handling climate refugee flows (Interpellation 2009/10:177; Riksdagens protokoll 2009/10:69).

Rising flows of climate refugees were increasingly framed as requiring stronger coordination at the European level for security and preparedness (SOU2007:60, part II, p. 472, Table 4.43). Several requests were made to push forward and influence the direction of discussions about CCM at the EU level. A harmonised migration system across the EU was not favoured, but intergovernmental cooperation based on guidelines and recommendations was welcomed, given the different types of migrants that the member countries received (Utlåtande 2006/07:SfU13). At the same time, calls were made for greater solidarity in receiving other categories of migrants, including environmental migrants, and for the EU asylum policy to become more welcoming amid declining refugee numbers. The Swedish Prime Minister was asked by the left-wing parties to link the two areas between migration and climate change in EU politics (EU-nämndens uppteckningar 2009/10:16, Interpellation 2009/10:177).

The existence of a legal clause protecting people from environmental disasters in Sweden likely influenced the debate on CCM at the EU level. In its Resolution 1655 (2009) *Environmentally Induced Migration and Displacement: A 21st Century Challenge*, the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe encouraged the European Union to use the ongoing amendment process outlined in its Policy Plan on Asylum to better address the protection gap in cross-border environmental displacement. In particular, Finnish and Swedish legislations and case laws were named for examining “whether they serve examples of best practice or even models for a new sub-paragraph explicitly recognising cross-border environmentally displaced persons in Europe”. A Swedish Liberal People's Party member, Tina Acketoft, was the reporter on behalf of the Assembly on the issue. She argued that migration and environmental issues should not be treated separately, but at the EU level, there was a lack of 1) an agreed definition on

people fleeing for climate effects, 2) a common legal framework, and 3) a responsible organisation.

Above all, right before the 2010s, there was a peak when Swedish politicians actively raised the issue of climate refugees through engaging multiple levels of actors. The discussion benefited from the growing visibility of CCM on the international stage, including the Copenhagen Summit in 2009, as well as Sweden's presidency of the EU Commission and the Nordic Council. Swedish politicians were in active contact with international organisations such as UNHCR. While there was consensus that the world's poorest would suffer most from the consequences, international politicians were divided over whether to link this more closely to refugee politics or to development work. Green Party politician Jan Lindholm reflected on the difficulty of working with the concept of climate refugees in international politics during the following interpellation. Therefore, the Swedish government promoted support for adaptation and disaster prevention through aid, while expanding the Geneva Convention to include climate-related refugees was considered risky and inappropriate (Riksdagens protokoll 2009/10:69).

“Through inquiries with various UN agencies, I have understood that the issue is inflamed and that no one really wants to address the issue of what I have chosen to call “climate refugees” but who many want to describe as “migrants”. The latter term, as I interpret it, would not entail the same responsibility for the international community.” (Interpellation 2009/10:177)

Shifts in Swedish political discourses on climate refugees after the 2000s were closely intertwined with international developments. As Jakobsson (2018, p. 85) notes, climate-induced migration attracted considerable attention in international politics during 2007-2008. Swedish national politics also saw a peak in engagement during this period. However, their framings differed. The international framing started with refugee protection, gained popularity with security, and, within this, covered vulnerability. The Swedish framing was always highly focused on refugee protection, and then vulnerability emerged with adaptation narratives. Moreover, even when security and preparedness were named, climate refugees were not positioned as a threat but as people in need of protection and support. In international politics, the 2004 Indian Ocean earthquake and tsunami had an immense impact on the formalisation of the norm proposition of disaster risk reduction (Jacobsson, 2018). In the analysed Swedish documents, although this significant event that affected many Swedes was not specifically mentioned, an emphasis on improving aid for monitoring disaster risk was clear.

In Interviewee B's view, in international politics, the securitisation discourse first boosted interest in the issue of climate refugees. While later moving towards adaptation, highlighting the human face enabled its inclusion in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) negotiations and, finally, acknowledgement in the Cancun Adaptation Framework, as there has been a tendency to be overly technical within the UNFCCC. Rather than the adaptation framing following the securitisation one, the two have co-existed over time and reinforced each other. She argued that “humanitarian actors have also sort of piggybacked a bit on the securitisation framing in order to propel interest” (Interviewee B). Although the Swedish framings seemed to rely far less on securitisation in the 2000s, this has changed since then.

The CCM issue cooled down considerably in the Swedish national politics after 2010, as reflected in the declining number of references in the document dataset. This matches Interviewee B's impression that the CCM topic did not receive so much research interest in Sweden in the 2010s. In 2016, the Swedish Ministry of Foreign Affairs commissioned SIPRI

to write a report providing an overview of climate-related security risks and policy responses to address them (Mobjörk et al., 2016). In this report, the security risk of climate-induced migration was examined (section 2.2.5), and the conclusion is that the risk primarily affects migrants. To take migrant as a threat to tighten borders would worsen human security. It was also clearly argued that, even in the case of large-scale migration, there was little evidence of conflict. Instead, migration occurred in already conflict-prone areas.

Interviewee D indicated that, in 2013, an important EU Commission Staff Working Document on “Climate Change, Environmental Degradation and Migration” (European Commission, 2013) likely affected Member States. It clarified that, given research suggesting a significant proportion of migration driven by environmental factors would occur within national borders, support resources should focus on developing countries. Moreover, the EU doubted whether a new, specific legal framework would be necessary and feasible, given that frameworks existed at the international and national levels that protect persons moving in the context of environmental change. Paradoxically, harmonisation with EU law became the justification for Sweden's removal of the special protection clause from the Aliens Act in 2021. This will be further explained in section 3.4.

Interviewee B does not think Sweden was active on the topic at the international level during the 2010s either. Sweden, as a small state, has been a rather successful norm entrepreneur in the EU and the UN in preventing violent conflicts. This is based on Sweden's international policy strategy, rooted in its foreign policy legacy and identity, and its desire to spread Swedish domestic values (Jakobsson, 2018, pp. 42–43). However, this did not seem to be the case with CCM. Interviewee B's study of climate-induced migration at the international level during the 2010s found no evidence that Sweden actively advocated for norms such as “climate-induced migrants should enjoy international protection”. The Swedish green and liberal think tank Fores published two reports on climate refugees for advising policy directions in the late 2010s (Jakobsson & Research Institute of Sweden, 2019; Karakitapoglu et al., 2018), but the initiative and funding came from the European Parliament, and the policy suggestions focused on the EU level.

In 2015, Sweden endorsed the *Agenda for the Protection of Cross-Border Displaced Persons in the Context of Disasters and Climate Change (Protection Agenda)*, developed by the Nansen Initiative, which identified practices to address the potential protection needs of people displaced across borders due to disasters and climate change. Otherwise, CCM was rather quiet in the Swedish national politics. One explanation may be the so-called European refugee crisis of 2015. Europe had the largest influx of refugees since the Second World War, and right-wing populist parties were on the rise in many European countries. This reduced its political will to enhance protection of refugee-like situations. This crisis thus impeded a major leap at the international level toward accepting the norm of protecting climate-induced migrants, despite the culmination of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) negotiations and the Nansen consultations. A strong group of advocates, all in favour of a major leap, was prepared to lobby for human mobility (Jakobsson, 2018).

In response to the refugee crisis in 2015, Sweden enacted a temporary Aliens Act in 2016, which curbed asylum applications by making temporary permits the norm, starting a significant shift in migration policy from generous to restrictive. The clause on environmental disasters was not included (Jakobsson, 2018: 141, footnote). In 2021, the amendments to the Alien Act formally and permanently removed this clause, which was justified to align Swedish legislation with the EU asylum acquis (EMN report 2023). The government bill on the revised Aliens Act (Proposition 2020/21:191) indicates that various bodies, including UNICEF Sweden, the Swedish Council of Refugee Groups, and Lund University, were consulted regarding the

revised rules in the Aliens Act. They expressed the need for a national protection ground that may expand in the future due to climate change. Thus, they believed that it should remain possible to grant a residence permit under this provision in cases where a foreigner cannot return to their home country due to an environmental disaster. However, these opinions did not help to keep the special clause in the revised law.

Peak 2: 2019-2020: handling the climate crisis through climate aid

Discussions of climate refugees rose slightly again towards the end of the 2010s with the strong institutionalisation of the Swedish climate policy. A leadership in climate transition is envisioned through a three-folded approach – Sweden as a good model itself, pressing big emission countries, and increasing climate aid (Riksdagens protokoll 2020/21:83). In June 2017, the Swedish Parliament adopted a climate policy framework which includes climate goals, a Climate Act and the Swedish Climate Policy Council (*klimatpolitiska rådet* in Swedish). Focusing on mitigation, the Climate Act requires that climate policy be based on climate goals and that current goals align with a timeline for emissions reductions (Government Offices of Sweden, 2021). Since 2018, the Swedish Climate Policy Council has released 8 annual reports in which it assesses the government’s overall policies in relation to the climate targets and issues recommendations.⁴ These reports focus on emission reductions and transitions across different sectors, but have connected climate policy to migration/mobility questions only in limited ways. In Sweden’s first Climate Policy Action Plan in 2018, only refugees were mentioned in the section on climate-related development work, as a consequence of climate change, poverty and conflict (Proposition 2019/2020:65, p. 179). Political discourses of the climate crisis adopted the notion of climate refugees as evidence of intensified climate change and expanding disastrous consequences for societies. Following this narrative, to centralise climate questions in foreign policy is justified (Riksdagens protokoll 2020/21:83). In an interpellation on the Swedish position before the COP25, Left Party politician Jens Holm stated:

“We are in a climate crisis. There is no doubt about it. In poor countries in particular, it is evident that thousands of people are becoming climate refugees every day. They are forced to leave their homes, often in rural areas, and move into big cities or flee to other countries. This is evident in countries like India, Bangladesh and the countries of sub-Saharan Africa.” (Interpellation 2019/20:103)

Climate change effects are no longer far away but could be felt closely in Sweden, for example, heatwaves, drought and wildfires in 2018. These are connected to climate refugees, which are supported by a bigger figure of 200 million by 2050 according to a UN report, to create an image of an alarming future for Swedish citizens. This alarming message underscored the urgent need for research into how to address this migration challenge in Sweden and across Europe, and what to do with potential mobility questions arising from the effects of climate change (Riksdagens protokoll 2019/20:52). The COVID-19 pandemic later reinforced the crisis narratives.

In the realm of development cooperation, there was an exploration of how to integrate climate-related security risks into the work of organisations such as SIDA. However, this integration seemed difficult even within SIDA, as its meaning differed by policy area, level, and unit (Brodén Gyberg & Mobjörk, 2020). Due to the multiplicity of the security and CCM concepts, attention is simultaneously based on conventional conceptions of threats and conflicts as well

⁴All the annual reports can be found in <https://www.klimatpolitiskaradet.se/en/publications/>

as the broader orientation towards borderless (human) development and resilience; together, it is recognised that it would be difficult to work long-term and with a preventive approach (ibid., p. 18). In parallel, climate aid was highlighted for being key to the support of vulnerable developing countries in climate transition, which both depends on Sweden's collaboration with international organisations and climate diplomacy (Proposition 2019/2020:65). Vulnerable regions and groups such as women and children in rural areas were highlighted for a higher chance of becoming climate refugees and thus need more aid support (Motion, 2019/20:159). However, given the unclear position of climate aid in the overall aid picture, there was both criticism of the limited budget constraining climate actions, including efforts to prevent climate refugees, and of occupying a budget that had previously been used for other aid actions (Riksdagens protokoll 2020/21:33).

Box 3. Key findings in period 2 (mid-2000s to 2020)

- The notion of climate refugee rapidly replaced environmental refugee with the growing interest in climate change.
- Climate refugees came to the focus of national debate rather than a side issue for a short period around the 2010s, coupled with the presidency of Sweden in the Nordic Council and the European Commission.
- Sweden was cited as an example for the legal protection of people displaced by environmental disasters, but the EU did not proceed to produce a harmonised legal framework.
- Left-wing parties, especially the Green Party, made consistent efforts to draw attention to CCM issues, through many ways, including using the Nordic Council mechanisms, inviting country visitors to the parliament to talk about the experiences of the issue, and talking to international organisation actors.
- Drawing on expanded research, the Swedish government claimed the impact of climate refugees on Sweden was indirect and limited despite extreme weather in Sweden making the climate crisis felt closer.
- Climate refugees were argued to be part of the strategies for Sweden to maintain its international leadership in environmental and climate questions.
- Globalisation reframed the Swedish geographical focus of climate refugees, shifting attention to Asia, especially Bangladesh, with a tendency to blur the difference between humanitarian aid and development.
- Studies show that it is difficult to incorporate CCM as part of climate-related security risks into the work of development cooperation institutions such as SIDA. As practitioners across different scales draw on different meanings of security and mobility, this often results in a fallback to meanings of CCM as threats and conflicts.
- Development cooperation practice in the form of disaster risk reduction and adaptation has already tended climate-related mobilities, but in a fragmented way, which is increasingly incorporated into actions under the umbrella of climate aid.
- The legal clause protecting people displaced by environmental disasters was not included in the temporary Aliens Act in 2015, constituting the start of a restrictive turn of Swedish migration policy. This clause was permanently removed in the 2021 amendments to the Aliens Act, justified by bringing Swedish legislation into line with the EU asylum acquis.

3.4 After 2020: pluralising CCM while restricting immigration

After 2020, the discourses of CCM have become more diffused but also clustered in the blocks of migration and refugee policy, development cooperation, and climate change governance. Political shifts between these blocks seem to steer both the main framing and policy within CCM.

Responsibilising supranational and international migration management

Internationally, Sweden employed various mechanisms to draw attention to climate-induced migration. For example, at the International Migration Review Forum 2022, Sweden delivered a national statement emphasising “adverse drivers of migration have worsened, compounded by global crises like the pandemic and climate change” (Olsson, 2022). In the voluntary Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration (GCM) review (Government Offices of Sweden, 2022), Sweden provided examples of how SIDA worked with FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation) to support food production in Burkina Faso, helping internally displaced persons withstand recurring climate shocks while enhancing vulnerable households’ resilience to prevent involuntary migration. However, in the GCM, Sweden did not commit to enhancing the availability of regular migration pathways in the context of disasters, climate change and environmental degradation (Daszkiewicz et al., 2024). At the 2022 Global Platform for Disaster Risk Reduction, a Swedish delegate emphasised that “drivers of risk such as conflict and forced migration are mitigated and sometimes even prevented” when early warning systems are established, adaptation measures are implemented, and resilience is localised (Ernkrans, 2022).

With the change of government in 2022 to a centre-right coalition in cooperation with the right-wing populist party, the Sweden Democrats, another paradigm of migration policy has emerged. On the Swedish Government website, it is clearly stated that “Sweden is redirecting its focus from being a country for asylum immigration to now being a country for labour immigration” (Government Offices of Sweden, n. d. a). Part of the priority of an orderly migration policy is the implementation of the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum, issued in June 2024, to tighten control of the EU’s external borders, adapt Swedish regulations to the minimum level according to EU laws, and prioritise returns (Government Offices of Sweden, n. d. b).

Sweden had momentum in discussions of climate-migration governance at the EU level while holding the presidency of the European Migration Network. At this network’s 2023 conference (EMNI, 2023), the conceptualisation of climate migration was clarified in two ways: First, most climate-induced migration is internal, occurring within national borders, and long-distance migration is uncommon. This justifies increasing aid and adaptation support in developing countries without changing immigration laws and regulations to accommodate this issue. Second, the meaning of climate migration was broadened to include labour migrants working in the green transition industries in Europe. This broadening might have a double-edged effect – while attracting more attention to the notion of climate migration, it risks reducing attention to the most vulnerable in need of protection. Also at this conference, in their speeches, both the Minister for Migration and the Director General of the Swedish Migration Agency emphasised the need for cross-border cooperation, increased knowledge, and support for global work, suggesting the need to address the “root causes” of migration (EMN, 2023). These ways of linking climate change and migration are substantiated by the simultaneous instrumentalisation of development cooperation and the greening of climate-related migration, as shown in the following two sections.

Governing CCM as part of the climate transition work

While CCM continues to be a side note in the Swedish national climate policy framework, new types of climate-related migrants have begun to be suggested, beyond displaced people from conflicts in the Global South, such as labour migrants to the Swedish agricultural sector, and migrants to work in industries for green transitions. In the 2021 report, a shortage of seasonal migrant labour during the COVID-19 pandemic is named as one of the challenges to the agricultural sector. However, it is considered to have a weak and indirect link to the sector's transition (The Swedish Climate Policy Council, 2021, p. 70). In the 2023 report, migration is named as one of the demanding tasks for the current government, but this was not connected to the climate target in any way (The Swedish Climate Policy Council, 2023, p. 41). In the 2024 report, it is said

“Opportunities for labour immigration are also crucial for the large new industries. The first wave of these is being set up in northern Norrland. This is an example of an area where the Government needs to ensure that climate policy is integrated into other policy areas.” (The Swedish Climate Policy Council, 2024, p. 99)

This quote exemplifies the expansion of climate-related migration amid green transitions. The statement suggests that policymakers consider climate policy overlaps with other policy areas, such as migration. In contrast, in the second government Climate Action Plan (Regeringens skrivelse 2023/24:59), migration is addressed only in a conventional way, framed under security and conflict concerns connected to the Global South.

CCM received increased attention as part of the Swedish government's efforts better to understand the impacts of climate change on Sweden, both from outside and within the country, to inform adaptation preparations. This was driven in part by the institutionalisation of Sweden's climate transition ambition and in part by the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Led by the National Expert Council on Climate Adaptation, the Swedish National Knowledge Centre for Climate Change Adaptation coordinates more than 30 agencies to develop information, tools, and research-policy exchange to strengthen society's ability to address the positive and negative effects of climate change in Sweden (EMNI, 2023). A series of reports was produced by organisations such as IVL, SIPRI, and SMB. Following a PwC report commissioned by the National Expert Council on Climate Adaptation, which identified human movement patterns as a key theme, IVL invited actors from diverse backgrounds to map a wide range of human mobilities that create both opportunities and challenges for Sweden (IVL, 2020). This report addresses not only immigrants driven by difficult living conditions in other parts of the world but also tourists, who are drawn to Sweden by its more favourable climate. Associated health and infectious disease risks were also highlighted, given the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic.

Although discussions of the impacts of extreme weather on societal vulnerabilities are increasing, mobilities are rarely mentioned in major agencies' publications (e.g., MSB 2024). When mentioned, for example, displacement is often considered to occur outside Sweden, such as disruptions to food supply with possible impacts on Sweden (MSB, 2022). In another MSB report studying preparedness in a changing climate (2023), however, it emphasises that the consequences of climate change in vulnerable countries could lead to increased climate-related migration and immigration to Sweden. An important exception is the first report on climate adaptation (2022), published by the National Expert Council on Climate Adaptation. This report considers the nature of climate change impacts on Sweden to be transnational, as Sweden is a small, open and industrialised country with a high level of dependence on other countries. It

predicts that an ageing and climatically more vulnerable Swedish society would need more immigrants, among whom some are forced to leave their homes due to climate change and vulnerable socioeconomic status (The National Expert Council on Climate Adaptation, 2022, p. 410). In addition, this report provides a comprehensive evaluation of human mobilities in the frame of climate risk and vulnerability (ibid., p. 560-565). With extensive references to research, it points out that the relationship between climate change and peace and security is highly complex; thus, even though vulnerable people and places may negatively affect Sweden through migration, such a scenario is uncertain. A series of predictions and scenarios on climate migrants is used to argue that climate-displaced people are indeed on the rise and could be very costly without immediate action. However, the report also highlights the scientific limitations of the cited numbers. This reflective approach, however, is not very common in official reports. By referring to the SIPRI report (Mobjörk et al., 2020), the adaptation report also highlights migration and mobility as one of the four interrelated pathways linking climate change and conflict, the other three being livelihoods, armed group tactics, and elite exploitation. During this time, Delmi, a Swedish government committee that provides migration research and knowledge to inform policy decisions, has published several reports, seminars, and podcasts on CCM. Besides emphasising a key message that any direct, linear, and causal link between climate change and migration risks environmental determinism and is misleading for policymakers (Czaika & Münz, 2022), other reports promote integrating migration into national climate adaptation strategies and including migrants in adaptation decision-making processes (Gemenne, 2022).

In the national political debates, when addressing the refugee questions, the Left Party continued emphasising Sweden's responsibility for climate refugees due to greenhouse gas emissions: "Even when it comes to climate refugees, we in Sweden have a great deal of responsibility through our greenhouse gas emissions." (Motion 2022/23:1230). The Left Party also emphasised the importance of addressing the underlying causes of people's flight. Climate change is named as one of the main causes that, through an indirect mechanism, contributes to political oppression, war and violence. "While we work for a humane and welcoming reception of people on the run, we must combat the injustices, inequality, wars, conflicts and climate change that are behind the flight" (Motion 2022/23:1230). However, all these motions were rejected by the parliament. Moreover, the current government's reduced engagement in climate and environmental policy has been heavily criticised by the opposition. Interestingly, when the Social Democratic Party leader Andersson criticised the government's reduced climate budget in the party leadership speech in the Almedals week 2023, a major Swedish political debate arena, she referred to, among other things, that the number of climate refugees may increase when the climate crisis ends up far down on the political agenda (FUF, 2023). In a similar way, in the parliament debate on emission reduction plan, the Green Party named climate refugees as one of the indirect effects that climate change may have, of which the Green Party argues that the Swedish government should take responsibilities to commit to emission reduction goals in order to reduce the risks of such effects, challenging the right-wing party Sweden Democrats' call for less engagement in the goals (Riksdagens protokoll 2023/24:84, p.76). In 2024 and 2025, two motions called "*A People's Movement for the Climate*" were proposed by the Centre Party to call for climate transition (Motion 2024/25:2954; Motion 2025/26:2798). The proposals call for sustainable, long-term solutions to address the growing number of climate refugees, but place responsibility at the EU and global levels.

"The parliament supports what is stated in the motion to urgently review the possibility of creating sustainable and long-term solutions both globally and at the EU level to secure the future of climate refugees, as the number of people in the world affected by

climate change will increase, and announces this to the government.” (Motion 2024/25:2954)

Instrumentalising development cooperation

The global progress in sustainable development and Sweden’s ambition to lead global environmental and climate issues naturally lead Sweden’s development cooperation to centralise the environment and climate. CCMs are claimed to be, in fact, long-standing in development cooperation practice. As the SIDA director Göran Holmqvist synthesised in his presentation at the EMN conference, SIDA has been addressing the effects of climate change on migration within the realm of the OECD/DAC (Development Assistance Committee) with five major intervention areas: 1) supporting developing countries hosting refugees, for example Rohingya in Bangladesh, 2) investing in disaster risk reduction, construction of shelter and early warning, which has started since early 90s after the cyclone Gorky 1991, 3) developing climate smart agriculture, 4) climate adaptation urban settings, and 5) shock-responsive social protection (Holmqvist, 2023). Among these, some measures directly intervene mobilities while the others, such as improving agriculture-related livelihoods and disaster risk reduction, have indirect implications. This suggests that different forms of mobilities are already covered in the fragmented picture of climate aid practice. Given that there are no specific rules or measures in place for climate-related migration and displacement, it is justified to address the issue of CCM as part of broader policies on development cooperation and humanitarian aid, or through projects and initiatives with countries from which climate refugees originate (EMNI, 2023). However, these practices characterised as project-based, short-term, and spread across different types of aid creates confusion in practice. For example, a survey of migration efforts among Swedish aid practitioners reports that the activities to date have been difficult to understand and that it is unclear what types of problems migration efforts are expected to solve (EBA, 2024, p. 24).

The formalisation of climate aid increasingly reframes questions about CCM. In describing climate aid, the current government emphasises a catalytic approach with “innovative solutions and private sector investment” (Government Offices of Sweden, n. d. c). Development cooperation is closely linked to climate and trade through the new *Strategy for sustainable growth, green transition and education (2025-2029)*. In this strategy, the term “involuntary migration” refers to the mobility effects of environmental and climate change and their impact on Sweden’s economy through global supply chains on which Sweden depends (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2025). Accordingly, strengthened climate adaptation is expected to prevent such involuntary migration. A recent report that evaluates the Swedish climate aid argues that “Sweden has established itself as an important player with a unique niche in climate Official Development Aid (ODA), a niche that should be preserved and strengthened.” (Brodén Gyberg & Fridahl, 2025, p. 11). Sweden has pioneered financing climate adaptation rather than focusing solely on emission-reduction aid, and it has an emerging catalytic approach to attracting private funds (Brodén Gyberg & Fridahl, 2024). However, research has just begun to map the scope of Swedish climate aid, which sector, which interventions and the effectiveness of the climate aid (Weitzel, 2024; Williams, 2023). No form of mobility is clearly mentioned in such efforts yet. However, in a motion proposed by the Social Democratic Party, increased climate aid is considered central to international efforts to help climate refugees, and both financial and technical support are highlighted as the main means of local adaptation to climate change (Motion 2024/25:3106). In contrast, the current government’s abandonment of the long-standing principle of allocating 1% of gross national income to development aid in 2023 could lead to a decrease in overall aid finance, with the risk of shifting existing ODA toward climate

rather than providing new and additional funds (Williams, 2023). The implications of aid reduction were critically questioned by the Left Party, considering people's situation in African countries such as Sudan is getting worse due to climate change on top of violence and conflicts (EU-nämndens uppteckningar 2023/24:34). At the Swedish Red Cross Forum 2024 themed "Climate Crisis as Human Crisis", Mattias Frumiere, Sweden's Climate Ambassador and Head of Delegation to UNFCCC, also highlighted the underperformance in terms of financing climate adaptation in the Global South and providing humanitarian needs due to the increase of demand and costs (Frumiere, 2024).

Significantly, the *New strategy for Sweden's global development cooperation on migration, returns and voluntary repatriation (2024–2028)* framed migration as a new strategic area for development cooperation (Government Offices of Sweden, 2024). The relationship between migration and development can be traced back a long way in Swedish politics, and it is intricate. This strategy emphasises "a particular priority is to safeguard Swedish interests in countering irregular migration and its risks, promoting return, voluntary repatriation and sustainable reintegration, and mitigating the root causes of irregular migration and forced displacement". This reflects a tendency to instrumentalise development cooperation and aid work to serve a restrictive immigration policy. Nevertheless, research already shows that proactive approaches to preventing conflict, supporting disaster preparedness, and facilitating reconstruction are more important than conditional aid for countries to accept their citizens who have been denied asylum in Sweden (EBA, 2024, p. 25).

Box 4. Critical reflections on the developmentalisation of climate migration in Bangladesh

Currently, Bangladesh sits on the front lines of the climate-development-migration nexus. In SIDA director Göran Holmqvist's presentation at the EMN conference, he said SIDA is proud to have been part of the first effort to construct cyclone shelters combined with early warning systems in Bangladesh. SIDA also supported via the Swedish Red Cross, and Bangladesh today is a model country for disaster risk reduction.

When debating the government's reform agenda for development assistance, the Minister for Migration Johan Forssell said,

“Then there is climate change. I was recently in Bangladesh and studied how it affects aid, linked to climate refugees. It is a concept that we might not have had just a few years ago, but I fear we will have to get used to it in the future.” (Utrikesutskottets betänkande 2023/24:UU8, page 61)

In research, Bangladesh is one of the hotspots for studying CCM and sea-level rise, which reflects the climate change challenge, but, in Interviewee A's view, there are many stereotypes about Bangladesh in this literature. Over the last decade, development aid to Bangladesh has been cut substantially. As Bangladesh has become a hotspot for climate change adaptation projects, its climate problem is often reduced to rising sea levels, despite the irregularity of the monsoon and the siltation of water bodies, which are the real major problems now that have severe environmental consequences. Interviewee A draws attention to how climate change has become a spice in discourses that frame how development issues are discussed, which hinge on structural problems of expert-led knowledge production and the donor system. Climate change is becoming a password for receiving funding because much of the donor and development budgets are allocated to it. This pre-determines the issue rather than being open to the empirical reality (Dewan, 2021). She warns that development practices are making climate-reductive translations of migration, “This is not riverbank erosion, it happens because the river moves, so yes, it is a valid reason for why people migrate, but to say that it is rising sea levels is actually incorrect”, she said. Many people migrate because of the salinisation of once-fertile lands caused by brackish tiger prawns. However, that is now cast as climate-induced migration, as if salinity were caused by rising sea levels rather than by land use.

Interviewee A argues that the real reasons for people moving are structural economic and political factors, such as underemployment, high costs of healthcare and education, and dowry costs. The aid system, such as microcredit, has exacerbated the situation. In the southwest coastal zone, it is like a development aid zone, as everything is project-based and donor-funded, but this does not contribute to long-term structure. Another perspective, Interviewee A offers, is that climate change is not causing gendered displacement. Rather, historically, women have always migrated for work in Bangladesh. There are complex social reasons and the need for supportive social networks to realise migration (Dewan, 2025). Gender is a complex concept, comprising interrelated social relations that shape the movements of different kinds of women. Similarly, rural-urban migration and children's experience are structural and aspirational factors, such as lack of jobs in rural areas, devaluation of manual labour and agricultural labour and aspirations to school, rather than being driven by climate change. Her critiques demand more critical thinking of how thoughts about vulnerable groups are integrated into development policymaking and practice.

Above all, in Interviewee A's view, with the new concept of climate mobility, it is hard to see how this could help to address the structural problems. As Dewan argues, “the current framing of migration as caused by climate change deflects attention away from how coastal vulnerabilities are fundamentally entwined with political structures of social and economic inequalities.” (2023, p. 2341).

Limited discussion of internal climate (im)mobilities

For the most part so far, climate-related migration has been framed as an issue occurring outside Sweden's national territory. However, there are emerging signs that policymakers are beginning to consider the implications of climate change for internal mobility. For example, at the Swedish Red Cross' 2024 Forum themed "Climate Crisis as Human Crisis", Mattias Frumiere referred to extreme weather "at home" in Europe to underscore the importance of development finance in fighting climate change in the Global South (Frumiere). Another example is that the Council of the Baltic Sea States considers evacuation, which means short-term mobility with the intention of moving back, as a relevant form of mobility in climate adaptation planning in the region (CBSS, 2023). Local authorities are advised to evacuate people to safe shelters in the event of major disruptions to societal services. This also means hotspots in need of evacuation are to be identified in the built environment, while considering the special needs of vulnerable groups such as the elderly and people with disabilities. When debating the national budget for municipalities, the Left Party member Ilona Szatmári Waldau argued for the need to prioritise investment in climate issues, otherwise this would be the biggest threat/costs in the future.

"Climate change will mean increased costs, including for securing coastal municipalities when the sea rises. We will have a different climate and a different way of growing crops. We will also have significantly more climate refugees in the world – we already have many, and we will have more." (Riksdagens protokoll 2022/23:44)

With the increase in extreme weather in Sweden, there is a shift in political debates from a reactive to a proactive approach, considering both rapid-onset events such as floods, wildfires, and snowfall, and slow-onset issues such as sea-level rise and coastal erosion. In other words, risk reduction and adaptation approaches are increasingly used to address risks and vulnerabilities in Sweden. This is different from the earlier, simple, positive assumption that Sweden benefits from a more favourable climate. However, in previous severe disasters, such as the record wildfires in 2018 and the floods in Gävle in 2021, the number of people evacuated was no more than a few hundred, and the number of internally displaced persons was 100 or fewer.⁵ Interviewee D's discussion with emergency coordinators suggested that a holistic infrastructure—comprising municipalities, insurance companies, and housing associations—seemed to enable timely evacuations and the provision of temporary accommodation, thereby making displacement a relatively minor issue. Despite concerns of evacuation in relation to other types of disasters, such as slides, which are rising in research discussions in the Swedish or Nordic context, and attention is especially given to small and marginal communities, mobility related voices are still marginal, simply as one means of climate change adaptation, in an emergent form of evacuation (e.g. Baron et al., 2024; Quinn et al., 2025).

The absence of complex thinking with internal CCM within Sweden is similar to that in most developed countries. Interviewee C, who specialises in studying Swedish political processes of climate change adaptation, did not notice any mobility concerns during her discussions with policymakers. She interpreted this as a reflection of the fact that climate adaptation is highly dependent on existing political and institutional structures that prevent policymakers from discussing mobility. In Sweden, climate adaptation is the responsibility of local government or

⁵ Statistics of the internally displaced population are from the database of the Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC). On the centre's website, there is also a news report about the evacuation due to wildfires in Sweden. <https://www.internal-displacement.org/news/heatwave-causes-unprecedented-and-deadly-wildfires-across-europe/> (accessed 7 November 2025).

municipalities. Although climate adaptation is required by law to be integrated into physical planning, municipalities are limited in their ability to advance climate adaptation measures, as they can act only on their own lands and on lands to be developed in the future. They can only try to negotiate the lock-in mechanisms, for example, by influencing strategies among property owners (Knaggård et al., 2025). It is hard to imagine how sensitive topics like relocation can be brought up, even though climate change puts certain areas at risk, for example, due to flooding. Mobility might become the new normal when considering the safety of residence in certain areas, but it is still presented as a future projection rather than the present. Currently, the costs of disaster damages are covered by insurance. However, if insurance becomes very expensive or no longer covers these costs, this mechanism might affect people's decisions to stay or move. However, although it is the responsibility of property owners to decide how to protect their properties, people may feel abandoned when the welfare state fails to provide the expected help. After Storm Babet swept the coast of Southern Sweden in 2023, there was a discussion about whether people should leave the unsafe areas exposed to high coastal erosion risk. However, houses were rebuilt, and people remained despite ongoing debate over who should be responsible for adaptation (Hallin et al., 2024). In situ solutions such as embankments are being tested. This suggests the immobility aspect is an important dimension in discussing the relationship between climate change and mobilities. Interviewee C suggests that it is increasingly necessary for policymakers to consider different scenarios of (im)mobility as part of climate adaptation governance in Sweden, as these have profound implications for vulnerabilities and inequalities.

In addition, as pointed out in the book *Nordic Approaches to Climate-related Human Mobilities* (Cullen & Scott, 2024), mobilities connected to the expansion of green transition industries are likely to be an increasingly important issue in the coming years, such as the displacement of indigenous peoples, not only physically but also culturally. Discussions relevant to such concerns were not found in the document analysis.

Box 5. Key findings in period 3 (2020 to today)

- The special clause in the Alien Act that protected people displaced by environmental disasters was permanently removed in 2021, with the justification of being in line with European laws.
- Sweden is active in responsabilising the EU and international level for the governance of climate mobilities.
- Climate mobility gets a new dimension of its meaning with the labour demand associated with green transitions. An expanding definition, however, risks reducing attention to the most vulnerable groups of climate migrants.
- The institutionalisation of Sweden's climate transition governance enables a richer understanding of the form and relevance of CCM to Sweden. However, such new knowledge seems to have a limited impact on climate policy.
- Climate aid became the main framing of climate refugees, highlighting technological innovation and industrial interests as part of the green transitions paradigm. However, the position of climate aid within the broader aid system is unclear, sparking debate over the financing of climate refugee prevention.
- As the components of climate aid and linkages to mobilities remain unclear, and the budget is not secured, the position of climate mobilities in this picture is unclear and uncertain.
- After the change of the Swedish government in 2022, development assistance and aid work are explicitly instrumentalised to serve a restrictive immigration policy.
- Climate mobilities are addressed in a very limited way in Sweden's domestic disaster risk reduction and adaptation policy and practice, mainly for evacuation. This can be explained by the structures of property, planning and insurance,
- There is no connection between policy discussion and Swedish internal climate mobilities and the international ones. Related terms, such as climate refugees, are assumed to be referring to people in the Global South.

4. Looking back, looking forward

This policy report aims to systematically map shifts in Swedish national policy and practice on the linkages between climate change and human mobilities. It contributes to further unpacking of the “puzzling state of affairs” of CCM (Curren & Scott, 2024, p. 1). In this Swedish case, the nexus between climate change and mobilities is examined through the under-explored lens of national-scale politics and historicisation. This Swedish case illustrates in a nuanced manner that political debates on CCM are not taking place in a vacuum but are deeply embedded in changing national political dynamics. Through the above analysis of the discursive trajectories over four decades, Swedish governance of climate mobilities appears as a contingent issue whose dynamics are tightly connected to three shifting fields: refugee governance, development cooperation and aid, and environmental governance. Due to the unclear normative proposition regarding climate-related migration, no single institution is clearly responsible for this issue; rather, it depends on the interests and strategies of the politicians to place the issue in different baskets of migration, environment, and development cooperation. It is clear in the findings that CCM has mostly been drawn on by left-wing parties in Sweden. Different from European countries, for example in Italy and Germany, where climate migration is increasingly actively framed by far-right parties as a threat and security issue (Bettini & Casaglia, 2024; Nash, 2024), the Swedish right-wings have not drawn on climate migration so much.

Statements on climate change and migration are shaped by the dialectic between government and opposition, with left-wing parties consistently driving the agenda or resisting cuts to aid, environmental protection and human rights. Over time, the norms on climate migration have shifted from solidarities, unequal trade relations, responsibilities, human rights, conflict, and security to climate aid, green transitions, and migration deterrence. There has also been a marked shift in the geographical imaginary of “where the migrants are” – moving from a focus on a distant Global South to seeing climate-affected mobility as an issue within Europe itself, yet still little seen as such within Sweden.

Although this report focuses on national-level politics, the findings show that national-level politics are interrelated with the EU and international levels of politics in terms of norms, positions, strategies, and practices. Previous studies show that European Union-level efforts have been limited and do not align with international efforts, and that calls for attention to the issue are scattered across several policy fields (Legut, 2022). It is uncertain if the Swedish strategy of appealing to the EU on the grounds of harmonisation can push forward innovative and effective practice at the EU level on the CCM issue. The history shows that, at the EU level, despite the identification of good examples such as Sweden and Finland around the 2010s, this did not lead to a real change in law or regulation. Being active in international institutions and mechanisms, such as the FAO, the Red Cross, and the IOM, mostly working through humanitarian aid and development cooperation, Sweden has been active globally in addressing human mobility in the context of climate change, disasters, and environmental degradation, through financial support, technical support, and knowledge production. However, it follows, rather than challenges, the approach of prioritising advocacy over institutional change. This multi-scalar interaction is likely to mainstream the developmentalisation approach of climate migration governance (Nash, 2024a).

The following final reflections highlight what we can learn from the past lessons and what the current Swedish political context may mean to Sweden’s engagement in the governance of climate mobilities.

4.1 Could the special legal clause be an inspiration for future legal innovations?

As shown, a special clause existed in the Swedish Aliens Act from 1989 to 2016 to protect people affected by environmental disasters. The clause’s existence reflected a long-term dominance of a humanitarian, human-rights-based approach in the Swedish political system. This was exceptional among the EU Member States except Finland and Italy. Surprisingly, this clause was rarely used. During the peak period 2007-2009, a Green Party member argued in a parliamentary debate for actively using this existing clause to protect people affected by climate change.

“Sweden has a provision in its immigration legislation to accept environmental refugees. This has only been used once, as far as I can remember, namely after an earthquake disaster in El Salvador, when many Salvadorans were granted temporary residence permits. Then they were allowed to go back, but they were still allowed to come after the earthquake. Could this section also be used for, for example, climate refugees?”
(Riksdagens protokoll 2008/09:102)

Ammer et al. (2022) show that over 2006-2019, only 181 judicial cases involved an individual expressly relying on the disaster to support an application to enter or remain in Sweden. The cases covered a diverse range of circumstances, from extending a temporary stay to already living in Sweden, and different types of disasters in the home countries. The Migration Agency

decisions attached to these juridical cases reflect a consistent approach to dismissing claims for international protection in the context of environmental disasters. Of the 181 claims, 91 per cent were dismissed on appeal. When the provision was applied, its interpretation was narrow, and decisions rarely reflected an individualised assessment based on specific country-of-origin information. This juridical practice culture is very different from that of Austria, for example. This study also highlights that, people who move to Europe or seek to remain here due to adverse environmental conditions in their countries of origin, enter through existing immigration law categories. This means that protection for people adversely affected by climate change is not only about protecting people out there in the Global South but those already in Europe.

Interviewee D argues that the absence of migration legislation that explicitly addresses climate or environmental dimensions contributes to a lack of interest among migration practitioners in working across communities of practice to explore linkages between climate change and migration. Fundamentally, the governance structure concerning climate mobilities remains siloed, separating internal from cross-border movement, and climate from migration. However, the earlier Swedish special provision still offers inspiration and lessons for innovating legal protection in relation to climate change and migration. Scott and Garner (2022) argue that the pioneering Nordic approach to creating an international protection category for people displaced across borders in the context of environmental disasters relied on cultural norms of solidarity, legislative norms, and international protection norms. However, as they also remind us, norm emergence is a slow process, and the wider social and political conditions must be receptive to these norms. These conditions do not look promising at the moment. Moreover, such new categories tended to raise conceptual confusion and to result in judgments applying more restrictive criteria than international human rights law. Thus, the recommendation for European-level governance that Scott and Garner proposed is that, instead of creating a new category of protection, efforts should focus on making the current humanitarian categories, which most EU Member States have, more effective.

4.2 The new context of national security and preparedness concerns

Several intertwined political dynamics have pushed national security and preparedness concerns to the top of Sweden's political agenda, including the Russian-Ukrainian war, Sweden's NATO membership, and the growing influence of populist right-wing parties. Political imaginaries of the "next crisis" and appropriate preparedness measures often invoke the COVID-19 pandemic and the 2015 European refugee crisis as key reference points. Since the change in the Swedish government in 2022, restrictive migration policies and practices have been unfolding rapidly, prompting strong reactions and resistance across societies. These measures affect not only asylum seekers but also labour migrants, both low-skilled and high-skilled. Statistics already show an increase in the number of migrants leaving Sweden (Statistics Sweden, 2025).

Against this backdrop, it has become more uncertain how the issue of CCM can gain sustained attention in national migration policymaking. Although in Sweden, compared to other EU countries, migration prevention has not historically been the key normative ordering concept in connection to climate change, but rather humanitarian narratives have dominated the discourse (Nash, 2024b), this is likely to change in the coming years. However, it could also mean that the left-wing parties become more active in fighting for a humane and welcoming migration policy. Although there are debates on whether a paradigm shift in migration policy is ongoing in Sweden, or if Swedish exceptionalism in terms of generous migration and integration policy

compared to other European countries is coming to an end, more research is needed to assess what current realignment of Sweden's migration governance means (Emilsson, 2025). Climate transition and development policy areas appear more likely than core migration policy to serve as entry points for promoting attention to CCM. For example, in recent motions, in motivating the policy change proposal, attention is called to understand the causes of involuntary migration, where climate change is named as one main cause, and thus, Sweden, as a contributor of greenhouse gas emissions, should be responsible for the protection of climate refugees (Motion 2024/25:1930; Motion 2025/26:2798). In a recent meeting of the EU-Committee, while the focus was on Ukraine, a Centre Party politician also used the occasion to highlight broader responsibilities towards people displaced by conflict and climate impacts:

“When it comes to migration, we can talk a lot and for a long time about what we agree on and what we do not. However, a question and a corollary is how to discuss the fact that there will be increased migration as a result of climate change. Is that preparedness in place? It is not just about primary climate refugees, but also secondary ones. How should the EU deal with this in the best possible way? I understand that the focus is on Ukraine and security for obvious reasons, but this will definitely be a challenge in the future, so it needs to be discussed now. Is this something that we will be able to do at all during the migration point?” (EU-nämndens uppteckningar 2025/26:18, p. 17)

To maintain Sweden's leadership in climate governance and development cooperation, and amid the emergence of a restrictive migration regime, CCM is currently framed within the space of climate aid in development cooperation. However, there are still many ambiguities in terms of how development and migration can be managed “in a way that is effective, coherent and consistent with core development principles” (Lindberg & Luthman, 2026). There is also a new initiative to broaden the scope of climate migrant to include labour migrants related to green transitions. These new directions, however, provide room for economic interests and further neoliberal development.

5. Policy recommendations

The following recommendations are proposed to Swedish policymakers for governing climate mobilities.

- Deepen collaborations with other states, particularly within the EU and Nordic frameworks, to share data, align positions, and jointly design responses on plural and interrelated forms of climate-related human mobility.
- Develop an interconnected policy discussion for overcoming the challenges in this nexus topic as well as for addressing cross-sectoral needs. A round-table mechanism should be established to bring together relevant national and sub-national actors to share experiences and propose a common work plan.
- Ensure that development cooperation and climate policy explicitly address climate-related (im)mobilities, focusing on long-term and place-based structural change, resilience building and risk reduction rather than only short-term relief.
- Systematically identify where protection is needed: preventing displacement, protecting people in transit, and safeguarding those already in Sweden (including under other migrant categories), and link each stage to responsible authorities and tools.
- Support research on better understanding processes and trajectories of climate-related (im)mobilities, using an intersectional and agency-centred perspective, and generate more empirical evidence on how climate aid is shaping climate mobilities.

- Balance ‘green transition’ labour needs with protection. When linking migration to green transition labour demand, ensure this does not marginalise the protective dimensions of internal and cross-border human movements.
- Building on Sweden’s earlier experience with protection in cases of environmental disaster, explore innovative legal pathways and policy instruments (e.g. temporary protection, humanitarian visas, complementary pathways) for protecting climate migrants.
- Connect domestic extreme weather governance with the governance of cross-border mobilities, and align CCM work with security and preparedness agendas.
- Pioneer rights-based climate mobility policies and research as part of Sweden’s broader leadership in sustainable development and climate justice in multilateral forums.

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